

RECEPTION OF THE FIRST BANK FIRSTMONEY APP AS A CUSTOMER SERVICE TOOL AMONG STUDENT CUSTOMERS

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Abstract: Customer service is becoming more demanding, and businesses are exploring various means such as technological means, to meet the rising challenges. This study examines the use of technological tools for customer services by commercial banks in Nigeria, focusing on the First Money app. While banks widely use techs like USSD, ATM, and online banking, the advent of mobile banking apps have revolutionized banking services and enhanced customer services in the country. It is necessary to substantiate this view through empirical means. Thus, four research questions were drawn, and an online survey was employed as a tool for data collection. A 16-item questionnaire was prepared and distributed to students of mass communication across six universities in southwest Nigeria. The results show that most of the student customers who use the First Money app are satisfied with the services they receive from the app. They attest that they now perform most of their banking activities on the app and visit fewer physical bank branches. Therefore, it was recommended that Nigerian banks should constantly review their app technologies to include more services, such as foreign concurrency payment, forex trading, and more utility services. The excellence theory and the technology acceptance model provide the theoretical framework for this study.

Keywords: Bank Application, Customer Rights, Customer Service, Digital Revolution, Online Banking

Introduction

Customer service has been a critical focus of modern organizations, as the customer's place in a business is important. The customer is called a king because their patronage brings income and their continued patronage ensures the survival of the organization. Customers are not only viewed as buyers or users of products and services, they are also considered as people who have special rights and must be protected from the harmful practices of business owners. Ajala (2001) stated that four basic customer rights were entrenched in the United States legal system in 1962, during the reign of John F. Kennedy as president of the United States of America. These customer rights were developed to protect customers and underscore the importance of customers to every business. The first customer's right is known as the *consumer right to safety*, which states that a product/service must not cause a consumer any harm. The second is known as the *consumer right to be heard*, which states that customer views must be respected. The customer right to choose states that the consumer reserves the choice to buy any product they choose. The *customer right to be informed* states that the consumer needs to be adequately informed about the goods/services. These consumer rights, as entrenched in the legal system of many civilized societies, form the bedrock of customer service in our modern society. While customers are increasingly becoming aware of their rights, organizations are exploring every means to improve their services. With the many alternatives available in the competitive business world, customers not only have many choices but could easily abandon a brand for another rival. According to Nnwanne (2015), customers are the most important public in any business organization because their regular patronage keeps in cash flow. Sam Black, a respected public relations scholar, believes that relations with customers depend on quality, price, and delivery time, and these all impact on the organization's reputation (Black, 1989).

Skinner, Von Essen, Mersham, and Motau (2010) stated that most organizations are starting to produce quality products/services because it is the only way to keep customers satisfied and retain their loyalty. Manipulating and coercing customers is inimical to business success, as the customer would eventually determine about the business brand. Skinner et al. advised that persuasion by enlightenment alone is the most effective way to retain a customer eventually. Ajala (2001) corroborated the above thesis by writing that the rising level of informed customers has led to increased customer awareness, knowledge, and expectations of product brands. Consequently, customers are now demanding for product/service quality, safety, rights, protection, and unique treatment. Organizations, especially the banking industry, which receives a large number of customers' activities every work day, have a high demand for good customer service. While face-to-face communication with organizational representatives and customers is the earliest form of customer service, digital platforms are now taking center stage in customer service. Although some scholars still believe that face-to-face service is still necessary (Grant, 2022). Recent technological developments have caused the automation of customer service. For example, in the banking industry, an ATM enables bank customers to perform self-help services outside the bank hall. The device reduces the number of customers who need to see a human customer service representative in the bank hall and saves customers plenty of time as services such as cash withdrawal, checking account balance, intra- and inter-bank cash transfer, and payment of utility bills can be performed on an ATM. According to Leung (2015), more and more organizations are providing customer service tools to encourage customers to have greater interaction with their brand. Organizations are using innovative technologies to provide customers with the tools they need to make purchases without having to step in the organizational office.

These technologies include organizational website and customer portals, sms, live chat, automated call-back, social media, discussion forums, online communities and mobile apps. In this era of smartphones and android phones, mobile apps have become an easy means of performing multiple functions, and online transactions have been greatly enhanced. The banking industry takes advantage of these technologies to make it easier for customers to access banking services. Although almost all banks in Nigeria have mobile apps, there is a need to examine the perception of bank customers and how they truly feel about using bank mobile apps to perform various banking services must be examined. Being one of the largest banks in Nigeria, First Bank Nigeria plc. was selected for this study, and the FirstMobile application was subjected to public opinion among Nigerian students' customers.

Statement of the Problem

In this digital age, business organizations are constantly seeking new means of interacting with their customers. Many digital platforms have been exploited as customer care service platforms, yet there are still some cleavages in customer services, such as convenience and timely accessibility. For example, customer relations management (CRM) has been helpful in saving customer details on a company's websites; however, the platform still lacked a very important function in a world defined by technological speed. The platform lacks an "instant" feedback mechanism and is not a tech that customers can interact with. Only management executives can use the CRM technology.

In this era of fast-paced communication, a delay in customer response can lead to a switch to a competitor's service or product. There are many competitors in telecommunications, banking services, and other industries as they all compete to lure customers with better services and fast two-way communication. Hence, the adoption of any new technology that will make two-way communication between organizational representatives and users faster and better. Many firms have adopted mobile banking apps to enhance the fast response to customer complaints and enable customers to perform fast tasks from the comfort of their homes, offices, etc. Therefore, this study examines the perception of the First Bank FirstMobile app for customer services because it has millions of customers and is one of the oldest banks in Nigeria. The crux of the study is to determine how many First Bank customers perceive the use of mobile banking apps to handle customer-related services.

Significance of the Study

With the many evolutionary changes that digital platforms are steering, tech tools like Bank App have become important communication tools for corporate organizations. Platforms like customer relations management (CRM) are widely adopted by business outfits to reach customers; however, there are barriers to reaching and receiving feedback from individual customers. Bank App has recently been adopted as a quicker and better way of establishing two-way communication with customers and making services more efficient. This study contributes to the evolving body of knowledge and understanding of the usage and relevance of digital technological platforms, such as bank apps, to corporate organizations.

Research Objectives

1. To assess customers' perception of Firstmoney as a platform for customer service by First Bank Plc.
2. To determine the disposition of First Bank Plc customers on Firstmoney App as a tool for customer services.
3. To determine the services rendered by FirstMoney as a customer communication tool by First Bank Plc.
4. To ascertain customer service satisfaction through the Firstmoney App by First Bank Plc.

Research Questions

1. What is the customers' perception of Firstmoney as a platform for customer service by First Bank?
2. What is the customers' disposition toward FirstMoney as a tool for First Bank's customer care service?
3. What are the services rendered by Firstmoney as a customer care communication tool by First Bank Plc.?
4. Are First Bank Plc. customers satisfied with the customer services they receive through Firstmoney?

Customer Service in the Digital Age

As noted earlier, customer services in organizations are the ways through which they attend to customer needs and retain patronage. Hoffman (2019) believes that because of increased customer information/enlightenment, expectations and services are now higher. Contemporary customers now request for fast, efficient, and value-for-money services. They do not just want to be treated with politeness but also with quality services, accessible to them anywhere. Jones (2023) corroborated Hoffman's assertion when she stated that contemporary customers are more conscientious and do their background findings before patronizing a brand. Hence, organizations are constantly seeking for better, faster, and more efficient means of connecting customers and providing them with the desired and expected services. This has led to the intersection of customer services and technology, as it is now common for organizations to combine multiple channels to attend to customers; devices, applications (Apps) and other digital platforms now largely support the human interface.

Since the advent of the Internet, many byproducts of the digital revolution have proved to be useful in many ways. In the field of communication, online platforms, social media, and apps have been largely adopted as means of group and mass communication platforms. Corporate organizations have explored and are still exploring digital technologies to improve internal and external communication. Human activities are generally believed to be better when digitalized as digital platforms are cheaper, affordable, faster, and user friendly (Webmaster, 2022). Virtually every activity performed in the corporate world is now being digitalized, and traditional methods are gradually being adopted. In the banking industry, customer service is one section where the staff experience higher requests and demands for assistance in performing transactions. In Nigeria, bank customer care units attend to hundreds of customers every working day, and bank halls are usually crowded with customers. One of the ways devised to handle this large customer request in the banking halls is the deployment of digital devices and technologies to decongest their premises. The new digital service platforms provide users with numerous alternative means to do transactions through emails, live chat, and in real time for immediacy and convenience (Virtual Incentives, 2023). The digital platforms used for customer services go beyond providing faster and more efficient solutions to customer problems; they also create personalized services for customers (Pascal, 2019).

Digitalized customer service platforms offer a personal experience medium to the customer. Organizations also need to collate and monitor their customer activities in one easy-to-control platform, and digital platforms provide this function. This gave rise to another technology called CRM. The CRM software helps management and users keep track of interactions, data, and information about customers and prospective customers. CRM software helps businesses track all connections and nurture relationships with their customers. It performs a broad range of activities, including managing customer data, enhancing marketing, and customer activities (Hotspot, 2023). In this digital age where people have access to multiple technological devices, apps, and digital platforms, CRM software helps organizations to store all customer information in one consolidated system and track their actions on other platforms. The system updates customer activities on the digital space and updates their data, allowing

the management to prepare online customer messages. A good example is the connection of bank users' activities on the Internet and every medium connected to the user banks. For example, when a customer performs transactions on his/her mobile app, the system automatically sends the information to the bank server, and SMS and email messages are sent to the user that transactions have been performed on their bank app. Details of the device used to perform the transaction, USSD, mobile app, on the phone or through the computer would be stated on the email, sms, or both. The CRM software has made all of these possible.

The Digital Revolution and Nigerian Bank Customers' Access to Services

Banks in Nigeria have become a norm to have mobile apps. In fact, every bank in Nigeria has a mobile application. While some banks have one mobile application, others have more than one. The rise of mobile apps has also given birth to new types of digital banking by non-conventional financial institutions, such as VFD, Opay, Palmpay, Kuda bank, and Moniepoint. Conglomerates and medium-scale businesses are now establishing virtual digital banking by creating mobile apps. For example, Air Tel Nigeria, a telecommunication company, has used its advantage as a communication firm to establish a financial organization in form of a digital application called Smartcash, similar to MTN, which started the trend with the Momo app. Reports have shown that while all financial institutions, large or small, now have mobile apps, only five of them have more than five million downloads (Akintaro, 2022). The five banks with over 5 million downloads are First Bank, Eco Bank, Guarantee Trust Bank, Zenith Bank, and United Bank for Africa. The First Bank mobile app, officially called Firstmobile, has one of the highest number of downloads on Google Play Store, with over 5 million downloads as of June 2022. With FirstMobile, bank customers now have easy access to their bank account and can perform various activities from the comfort of their home or office, regardless of where they are, without having to visit the banking hall. Intra-banking, inter-banking, money transfers, payment of utility bills, airtime purchase, checking of account balance, and basic customer enquirers are all possible. Through the FirstMobile app, customers can view transactions and receive up to two months' back transaction receipts that can be easily shared through social media platforms from the bank's mobile app.

The bank's mobile app also allows customers to perform many other functions, such as programming payment ahead, and reminds customers of important international events, such as Mother's Day, International Women's Day, World HIV/Aids Day, and Cancer Day. The app saves customer's beneficiary's account details for ease of cash transfer. All services are assessable 24 hours a day, 7 days a week, making customer-related services available to its customers anytime of the day and at their convenience. Almost all services for which people visit bank halls are now done on bank mobile apps (Simon, 2022). Several other ways bank customers now access services through digital platforms exist. For example, Firstbank Nigeria has the following means through which their customers can easily access services: Payment channels, USSD, online banking, and chat banking.

Payment channels: This mobile means of payment transactions includes cash withdrawal and cash transfer, as well as automated teller machines (ATMs) and point-of-sale terminals (POSs). The First Bank ATM, like many other banks, is a 24 h self-service platform where customers can withdraw cash, transfer funds, pay bills, top up airtime, and make mini-account statements. The point-of-sale terminal is a portable handheld device that accepts cards (debit cards) for the payment of goods and services. The POS service has enabled banks to reach customers in remote areas where bank facilities are unavailable.

USSD: one of the electronic means Firstbank adapted to help customers perform convenient service. The Bank USSD (Unstructured Supplementary Service Data) enables customers to perform various banking transactions,

such as money transfer, opening account, checking account balance, paying bills, buying airtime, and paying for goods and services. The general code for First Bank USSD is *894#, and customers can use any type of phone because it does not require internet connectivity or data. Many customers still use the USSD even after introducing the mobile application. Virtually all services available on the bank mobile app are performed through USSD.

Online Banking: In the wake of digital online business in Nigeria, banks have adopted online platforms to reach customer care services, i.e., email letters, credit/debit alerts, sma, etc. The customers have access to information about their banking activities, such as withdrawals and credit details, and receive weekly, monthly transaction reports with account balances. These are augmented with sms (Enterprise Time, 2025). The First Bank's online banking service is called FirstAlert and works 24 hours a day, 7 days a week. Notifications of transactions from registered accounts are conveyed to the account holder on a regular basis.

Chat Banking: Social media platforms like WhatsApp present useful features, and banks have taken advantage of it to engage customers in virtual chat relations. Customers can now do that from the comfort of their phones instead of walking into the bank branch and queue to speak to a customer care agent through WhatsApp. At the time of this study, the Whatsapp number for all account holders is 08124444000.

Theoretical Underpinning

This study is about two separate things connected to bank customer services. First, customer services and this aspect of public relations functions are enhanced with the aid of technology. Therefore, this study examines two relevant theories to help marry the two distinct functions. Hence, the Excellence Systems theory of public relations and technological determinism theories are reviewed.

Excellence Theory

Public relations scholar James Grunig assembled a team of researchers and PR experts (Larissa Grunig, David Dozier, William Ehling, Jon White, and Fred Repper) into a two-decade study to examine the value of PR to an organization. The Research Foundation of the International Association of Business Communicators (IABC) commissioned this study in 1984. After a decade of rigorous quantitative (Survey-Questionnaire) and qualitative (Interview) research of more than 300 organizations in Canada, the United Kingdom, and the United States, ranging from corporate, nonprofit organizations, and government agencies, the Excellence Theory was born. The core of the excellence theory was the result of a survey and interviews with over 5,400 executives, PR practitioners, and employees (Waddington, 2012). The crux of the theory is that for an organization to be effective, it must behave in ways that solve problems and satisfy the goals of stakeholders and management (Martin, 2020). Grunig (2010) reasoned that if the organization fails to do so, the stakeholders would either pressure the organization to change or oppose it in ways that add cost and risk to organizational policies. This study focuses on the excellence of customer service, which is a function of public relations, and examines how Nigerian banks have adopted new media technologies (the Internet, digital devices, social media, and apps) to ease services for both their staff and customers. In support of this theory, the theory of technological determination is reviewed.

Technological Determinism Theory

In a broad application, technological determinism is a sociological paradigm that touches many aspects of human activities in society. It is a theory that points to technology as the center of human society's development. Technology shapes the social world, cutting across language, communication, military, business, engineering,

etc. Since ancient times, every discovery and invention of technology changed how humans go about their activities and contributed to better ways of doing things (Gill Singh, 2023). When cars, steam engines, planes, etc., were developed, they altered the human mode of transportation, and the emerging machines continue to improve human conditions. In the media parlance, technologies such as radio, telegraph, fax, television, the Internet, and social media have all impacted human communication, and their newer versions are making communication faster, more affordable, and better. Scholars such as Harold Innis, Karl Marx, Marshall McLuhan, and others explain how technologies have shaped human society over the years. In our field of mass communication, technological determinism, as propounded by Marshal McLuhan (1962), states that media technology shapes how humans think, feel, and act, and the social world revolves around the technology prominent in that age/in a particular age. He argued that how we use current technology shapes our activities. For example, before the advent of radio technology, the printing press products (books, newspapers, and magazines) required full attention of our eyes and minds and literacy. When radio was invented, humans were required to listen and develop only the sense of hearing. In this age of the Internet and social media, human communication is becoming more all-encompassing. The ontological assumption of this theory states that humans have no free will to decide how they want to communicate but are compelled to adapt to the medium used in society to avoid being isolated. The epistemological assumption about the truth of this paradigm is that change in technology also leads to change in the way people communicate in a society, i.e., social media is used in an informal setting and messages are sent in a casual manner. Its axiology states that herd's behavior will be evident among groups of people using a particular medium to communicate (Griffin, 2000; West & Turner, 2000). This study focuses on how modern communication technologies, such as social media and the Internet, especially apps, have enhanced how bank customers transact business and communicate with their banks.

Research Method

Conducting research in this technology-driven society means that the researcher must find better means of reaching the target audience with ease. Today, a large amount of the modern population can now be reached online. Data show that there are currently over 5.2 billion internet users worldwide, and reaching them is easier than in the pre-internet age (Kumar, 2025; Genuns, 2025). Therefore, this study did not only employ a survey but also used an online survey, given that the study's target audience is university students who spend a lot of time online (Dubey, 2025; Alves, 2025). A-probability sampling technique was used to reach First Bank's student customers who use the FirstMoney app. using convenience sampling was necessitated by the fact that not all students use the same bank, and a stringent goal of reaching only those student customers of First Bank who use the FirstMoney app was established. Therefore, the study population was selected due to the primary relevance of the target audience to the original purpose of the study (Tejumaye, 2003; Salami & Oginibo, 2002; Statistics, 2018; Mishra, 2021; Kibuacha, 2021). Hence, the mass communication students of universities in Southwest Nigeria were selected, while the mass communication departments in the following universities were reached by snowballing, to fill the 16-item questionnaire prepared based on the 4 research questions: Lagos State University of Science and Technology (LASUSTECH); Caleb University, Lagos; Adekinle Ajasin University, Ondo State; Christopher University, Ogun State; Wesley University, Ondo State; and the NOUN annex Ikorodu.

Data Presentation

Table 1: Gender representation of respondents:

Item	Frequency	Percentage
Male	32	29.4%
Female	77	70.6%
Total	109	100%

Over 70% of the student customers surveyed are females. However, this is because most mass communication students across the country are females (Abati & Ayoola, 2019).

Table 2: Age bracket of respondents:

Years	Frequency	Percentage
16-20	44	40.7%
21-25	28	25.9%
26-30	20	18.5%
31 above	16	14.8%
Total	108	99.9%

As seen in the above table, approximately 42% of the respondents are very young, and this is due to the fact that Nigeria currently has a population dominated by youth (about 70% of Nigeria's population are youths and 60% are below 30 years old; Moses, 2025).

Table 3: Academic program of respondents:

Item	Frequency	Percentage
NCE/ND	24	23.1%
BSC/HND	72	69.2%
Postgraduate	8	7.7%
Total	104	100%

The number of undergraduates surpassed that of postgraduate students across the country, and this influenced the number of respondents in the above table (Oconnell, 2025).

Table 4: Religious affiliation of respondents:

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Christianity	91	83.5%
Islam	16	14.7%
Traditional/indigenous belief	0	0%
Others	2	1.8%
Total	109	100%

Although official records show that there are more Muslims than Christians in Nigeria, this survey was conducted in southwest Nigeria, where many Christians are faithful (Chukwu, 2025).

Table 5: The FirstMoney app provides many customer services they need:

Response	Frequency	Percentage
SA	28	25.7%
A	45	41.3%
D	30	27.5%
SD	5	4.6%
Don't know	1	2.7%
Total	109	100%

Over 67% (SA + A) of the respondents agreed that the FirstMoney app provides many customer services. This is critical to contemporary customers who want many things done from the comfort of their computer and phone screens.

Table 6: On the FirstMoney app, the following services are performed with ease:

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Cash transfer	16	14.7%
Online shopping	0	0%
Payment of the utility bills	4	3.7%
Checking the account balance	14	12.8%
All of the aforementioned	75	68.8%
Total	109	100%

As seen in the above table, almost all respondents used the FirstMoney app for cash transfer, paying utility bills, and checking account balance. Customers indicated that the FirstMoney app is used for many commercial services.

Table 7: Customers' most commonly used tools for making transaction:

Response	Frequency	Percentage
First Bank app	58	53.2%
First Bank USSD	15	13.8%
First Bank WhatsApp	2	1.8%
First Bank Linkdn	0	0%
All of the above	34	31.2%
Total	109	100%

Most FBN student customers use the FirstMoney app for transactions (53%), about 14% mostly use USSD, and about 2% use the WhatsApp platform. Moreover, 31% of respondents use all of these First Bank tech platforms for customer services. As seen in the table, the FirstMoney app is the most used tech platform by student customers for transactions.

Table 8: The FirstMoney app is easy to use:

Response	Frequency	Percentage
SA	45	41.3%
A	40	36.7%
D	2	1.8%
SD	1	0.9%
N	21	19.3%
Total	109	100%

Almost 80% (SA + A) agreed that downloading the FirstMoney app is easy. Ease of downloading phone and computer applications is another factor that encourages or discourages customers from patronizing a business. The respondents agreed that the FirstMoney app is easy to download.

Table 9: The FirstMoney app is easy to use:

Response	Frequency	Percentage
SA	32	29.4%
A	45	41.3%
D	4	3.7%
SD	2	1.8%
N	26	23.9%
Total	109	100%

As seen in the above table, approximately 70% (SA + A) agreed that the FirstMoney app is easy to use. Usability is another factor to consider when designing an app, as customers would easily move on to the next app when they find it difficult to use. The ease of use plays a key role in retaining customers to continue patronizing a business.

Table 10: The FirstMoney app makes banking easy for me

Response	Frequency	Percentage
SA	33	30.3%
A	37	33.9%
D	6	5.5%
SD	2	1.8%
N	31	28.4%
Total	109	100%

Almost 65% (SA + A) of the student customers agreed that the FirstMoney app makes banking easy for them. However, 28% were indifferent.

Table 11: Customers began visiting the bank branches less often after they started using the FirstMoney app

Response	Frequency	Percentage
SA	33	30.3%
A	38	34.9%

D	10	9.2%
SD	1	0.9%
N	27	24.8%
Total	109	100%

About 65% (SA + A) of the respondents began visiting First Bank less frequently, as they use the FirstMoney app. However, about 25% were indifferent to this question. Overcrowded bank halls used to be a major challenge for many Nigerian banks. However, with the introduction of digital platforms, such as bank apps, many customers now conduct most of their financial transactions from their phones. This means that the First Bank staff at the customer care unit now attend to a lesser number of customers at their physical branches.

Table 12: The high FirstMoney app charges

Response	Frequency	Percentage
The charges are worth the services	36	33%
They are not worth the charges.	10	9.2%
The app does not charge the user	8	7.3%
App charges are grossly uncalled for	8	7.3%
No comment	47	43.1%
Total	109	100%

Although 43% of the respondents were indifferent to this question, 33% believed that the charges applicable to transactions on the FirstMoney app are worth the services. Approximately 9% believe the charges are not worth it, while 7% were not sure if the app charges for services. With good and efficient services, customers often overlook the charges. However, in the case of high charges, customers also protest and even boycott services. In this case, users of the FirstMoney app believe that they get the desired services at reasonable charges.

Table 13: Customers now pay most of their utility bills through the FirstMoney app at their convenience

Response	Frequency	Percentage
SA	26	23.9%
A	40	36.7%
D	10	9.2%
SD	1	0.9%
N	32	29.4%
Total	109	100%

Approximately 61% (SA + A) of the customers now pay most of their utility bills through the FirstMoney app, while 29% remain indifferent. The implication for the customers is that they would visit the bank branches only when they cannot perform a transaction on the FirstMoney app.

Table 14: Other customer tech platforms, such as USSD and First Bank WhatsApp, are better than FirstMoney

Response	Frequency	Percentage
SA	8	7.3%
A	18	16.5%
D	42	38.5%
SD	5	4.6%
N	36	33.8%
Total	109	100%

About 43% (D + SD) of the customers do not agree that other tech platforms are better than the FirstMoney app. Only about 24% of respondents agreed with the statement, and 34% remained indifferent. By implication, a good percentage of student customers believe that FirstMoney is better than other tech means of transactions, such as USSD.

Table 15: FirstMoney gives customers difficult moments a lot

Response	Frequency	Percentage
SA	8	7.3%
A	22	20.2%
D	30	27.5%
SD	4	3.7%
N	45	41.3%
Total	109	100%

About 31% (D + SD) of the respondents do not agree that the FirstMoney app gives them difficulty for a long time, but 28% (SA + A) said they experience difficulty for a long time. However, about 41% were indifferent on this. The figures of those who believe that the FirstMoney app does not give them frequent issues are more than those who said they do have frequent issues.

Table 16: The FirstMoney app is better than other local banks' apps

Response	Frequency	Percentage
SA	21	19.3%
A	23	21.1%
D	15	13.8%
SD	5	4.6%
N	45	41.3%
Total	109	100%

About 40% (SA + A) of the customers believed that the FirstMoney app was better than other local bank apps, while 18% (D + SD) thought otherwise. By implication, the figures show that a fair percentage of the student customers find the FirstMoney app to be better than other local bank apps.

Answering the Research Questions

1. What are the customers' perceptions of First money as a platform for customer service by First Bank?

Collated responses reveal the perception of customers on the First Money app. As shown in Table 5, over 67% (SA + A) of the respondents agreed that the First Money app provides the customer services they need. This is critical to contemporary customers who want many things done from the comfort of their computer screen. Table 6 reinforces this perception as the respondents agreed that they use the First Money app for cash transfer, utility bill payment, and checking account balance. Customers indicated that First Money is used for various commercial services. These results show that students' customers of First Bank who use the First Money app see the app as a customer service platform where they can easily perform many banking transactions.

2. What is the customers' attitude toward FirstMoney as a tool for First Bank's customer care service?

Customers' disposition toward the First Money app could be seen in their response on Table 7, where data shows that most FBN student customers, 53% use the First Money app for transactions, about 14% mostly use USSD, while about 2% use WhatsApp platform. Customers who use this bank app use the First Money app more than other bank services tech platforms. As seen in Table 11, approximately 65% (SA + A) began visiting First Bank branches less frequently, as they use the First Money app. However, about 25% were indifferent to this question. As seen in Table 13, about 61% (SA + A) of the customers now pay most of their utility bills through the First Money app, while 29% remain indifferent. Table 10 reveals that 65% (SA + A) of the student customers agreed that the First Money app makes banking easy for them. However, 28% were indifferent. These data show how customers see the First Money app as reliable and rely on it for many transactions.

3. What are the services rendered by First money as a customer care communication tool by First Bank Plc.?

The First Money app renders many bank services that were previously only accessible by customers at bank branches. As shown in Table 6, the First Money app is used for various banking services, such as cash transfer, utility bill payment, and checking account balance. Customers indicated that the First Money app is used for many commercial services. Before the advent of the First Money app, customers had to visit bank branches to perform many crucial banking services. Although tech platforms such as USSD and ATMs began rendering some of these services, bank apps have enhanced these earlier customer care technologies.

4. Are First Bank Plc. customers satisfied with the customer services they receive through First money?

When asked these questions, the student customers indicated their satisfaction with the First Money app. Table 12 shows that 33% of the belief charges applicable to transactions on the First Money app are worth the services. Approximately 9% believe the charges are not worth it, while 7% were not sure if the app charges for services. This shows that most of the student customers are satisfied with the service they receive because they believe that whatever cost of charges is involved is worth the services obtained from the bank app. In Table 14, the customer defended their choice in Table 12 by arguing that other customer tech platforms are not better than the First Money app. Table 14 shows that about 43% (D + SD) of the customers do not agree that other tech platforms are better than the First Money app. Only about 24% of respondents agreed with the statement, and 34% remained indifferent. The data in Table 16 reinforces this view as it reveals that approximately 40% (SA + A) of the customers believe that the First Money app is better than other local bank apps, while 18% (D + SD) thought otherwise.

Summary

Public relations scholars, such as Nwanne (2015) and Black (1989), argue that customers are the most important public in any business organization because their regular patronage keeps in cash flow. The renowned British PR scholar Sam Black (1989) believes that relations with customers depend on quality, price, and delivery time, all

of which have a huge impact on the organization's reputation (Black, 1989). While businesses are expanding, they face the challenge of handling customers' many requests. If not strategically handled, those organizations overwhelmed by customer demands would lose their market share to competitors with better customer services. This was further complicated by the massive education and enlightenment of customers who are now aware of their rights. Organizations are turning to more efficient means and platforms to handle the rising customer demand for fast, cost-effective, and quality services (Ajala, 2001). Thus, many organizations, especially banks, have turned to electronic modes of customer service. This study was set to explore the banking sector's customers' attitude toward modern tech-driven customer service platforms. For ease of study, a particular bank was selected, and its mobile app became the subject of discourse. Therefore, this study aims to determine how many First Bank customers perceive the use of mobile banking apps to handle customer services.

Conclusion

After reviewing the relevant literature and outlining the direction of this study, four research questions were asked, and data were collected using a survey. University students in Nigeria who use the First Bank First Money app were selected from across universities in southwest Nigeria. A 16-item questionnaire was drawn from the four research questions and served to undergraduate and postgraduate students of the 6 universities reached using the snowballing method. The findings reveal that bank customers expect efficient and fast services from their banks, and they see the bank app as a quick means to receive timely services. The respondents in this study have a positive perception of the First Money app, as most of them indicated how they perform many banking services on the app. They attest to how easy it is for them to access services such as cash transfer, checking account balance, and paying utility bills, all from the comfort of their phones through the First Money app.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, the following activities are proposed:

1. As a matter of fact, First Bank (and other commercial banks in Nigeria) should keep reviewing their mobile applications for efficient upgrade. Since it is now established that this app has reduced the workload of customer service and that it is the new norm in modern customer service, it must be constantly subjected to professional and technical review for better performance.
2. Banks must also forge close alliances with fintech researchers and app developers to explore many other features of customer services that are not currently performed on the app. For example, include more payment options for utility services, such as transportation fare and booking flights.
3. The banks should include more services on the app, such as sending and receiving foreign currencies and checking the exchange rates of naira to foreign currency.
4. Banks should make an effort to encourage more customers to download and use apps for ease of transaction.

References

Abati, M.O. & Ayoola, M. J. (2019). Career choice in journalism among female mass communication students of the federal polytechnic, Ilaro. 1st National Conference of WITED, Ilaro Chapter. Ilaro Federal Polytechnic August 13-16, 2019. pp: 157-166

Ajala, V. O. (2001). *Public relations in the search for professional excellence* Revised Second Edition. Mayest Publication.

- Akintaro, S. (2022). *Top 5 banking apps in Nigeria that have crossed 5 million users Downloads on the Google Play Store*. Available at: <https://nairametrics.com/2022/07/30/top-5-banking-apps-in-nigeria-that-have-crossed-5-million-downloads-on-google-play-store/>
- Alves, J. (2025, June 25). Effectively conducting an online survey in 12 steps. Available at: <https://chattermill.com/blog/how-to-create-an-online-survey>
- Black, S. (1989). *Introduction to Public Relations* West African Book Publishers Limited.
- Capstone, (February 2001). *Technological Determinism Theory* Available at: <http://www.uky.edu/~drlane/capstone/mass/determinism.htm>
- Chukwu, O. (June 13, 2025). Explain all types of religions in Nigeria. Available at: <https://nigerianqueries.com/types-of-religions-in-nigeria/>
- Daphne, (2022). *Old McLuhan on the new media*. Available at: <https://bettermarketing.pub/old-mcluhan-on-new-media-953f3bb90f71>. Accessed on: 26/10/2022
- Dubey, S. (2025, February 21). 7 Conducting a survey: best practices, tools, and more Available at: <https://qualaroo.com/blog/how-to-conduct-a-survey/>
- Entreprise Time (March 24, 2025) How to enroll/register for First Bank's internet banking and mobile app. Available at: <https://etimes.com.ng/how-to-enroll-register-for-first-bank-mobile-app-and-internet-banking/>
- Genus, R. (2025, February 19). How many people use the Internet? Available at: <https://soax.com/research/how-many-people-use-the-internet>
- Gill Singh, K. (2023, March 23). *Technological technology theory: 5 examples, pros and cons*. Available from: <https://helpfulprofessor.com/technological-determinism-theory/>
- Grant, M. (2022, April 7). *What is customer service and what makes it excellent?* Available from: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/customer-service.asp>
- Griffin, E. (2000). *A first look at communication theory*. 4th ed. Boston, MA: McGraw Hill.
- Grunig, J. E. (2010). *Excellence theory in PR* Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Hoffman, F. (October 1, 2019). *Providing excellent customer service in the digital age*. Available from: <https://www.ideafit.com/personal-training/providing-excellent-customer-service-in-the-digital-age/>
- Hubspot, (2023). *What is CRM?* Available at: <https://www.hubspot.com/products/crm/what-is>

- Jones, R. (2023). *Importance of customer service in today's digital age* Available at <https://www.sbmarketingtools.com/importance-customer-service-todays-digital-age/>
- Kibuacha, F. (2021, April 6). *Determining the sample size for a study*. Available from: <https://www.geopoll.com/blog/sample-size-research/>
- Kumar, N. (May 13, 2025). How many people use the internet in 2025 (latest data). <https://www.demandsage.com/internet-user-statistics/><https://www.demandsage.com/internet-user-statistics/>
- Leung, S. (2015, January 20). *12 customer services tools that will make your customers' Lives easier*. Available from: <https://www.salesforce.com/blog/12-customer-service-tools-that-will-make-your-customers-lives-easier-3/>
- Martin, M. (2020, May 31). A theory of excellence in public relations? Available at: <https://www.bymelissamartin.com/post/blog-b-long>
- McCombs, S. (2022, January 13). *Research design: a step-by-step guide with an example*. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/research-design/>
- McLuhan, M. (1962). *The Gutenberg Galaxy: The Making of Typographic Man* Toronto: University of Toronto
- Mishra, P. (2021, June 19). 8 types of sampling techniques. <https://towardsdatascience.com/8-types-of-sampling-techniques-b21adccd2124>
- Moses, O. (2025, July 18). Nigeria's youth majority: 60% of population under age 30—NPC. Available at: <https://leadership.ng/nigerias-youth-majority-60-of-population-under-age-30-npc/>
- Nnwanne, B. U. (2015). *Performing functional public relations*. University Printing Press, State University.
- Oconnell, L. (2025, May 22). Nigerian university graduates: Tracking the numbers Available at: <https://shunstudent.com/article/how-many-students-graduate-from-nigerian-universities>
- Pascal. (October 25, 2019). *6 tips for personal customer service in the digital age*. Available from: <https://www.userlike.com/en/blog/personal-customer-service>
- Salami, O. R., & Oginibo, E. O. (2007). *Research Methods and Precision Journalism* Akure: Panama Press.
- Simon, J. (2022, May 2). *The 10 best mobile banking apps of 2022*. Available at: <https://smartasset.com/checking-account/2018-best-mobile-banking-apps>
- Skinner, C., Von Essen, L., & Mersham, G. & Motau, S (2010). *Handbook of the public relations*. 9th ed. Oxford University Press.

- Tejumaiye, J. (2003). *Mass Communication Research: An Introduction* Ibadan: sceptor Prints Limited.
- Virtual Incentives, (2023). *Customer Service in the Digital Age* Available at: <https://www.virtualincentives.com/6-expectations-of-customer-service-in-the-digital-age/>
- Waddington, S. (2012, August 27). *A Critical Review of Excellence Theory in an Era of Digital communication*. Available from: <https://www.wadds.co.uk/blog/2018/7/18/a-critical-review-of-excellence-theory-in-an-era-of-digital-communication>
- Webmaster, (2022). *Customer Service in the Digital Age: What You Need to Know* Available from: <https://www.techulator.com/resources/20698-customer-service-in-the-digital-age-what-you-need-to-know>
- West, R. & Turner, L. H. (2000). *Introduction to communication theory: Analysis and application*. Mountain View, CA: Mayfield.